

Study on the mechanical and electrical properties and creep behaviour of carbon fiber nano-composites

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ABSTRACT

Recently, it is been observed that surface modification of carbon nanotube influences on CNT's distribution among epoxy resin and affects the mechanical properties and electrical conductivities of CNTs. Owing to above-mentioned effects, carbon nanotubes treated with oxidizing in organic acids, a kind of surface modification, generates functional groups on the surface of CNTs is a major investigation in this study to enhance mechanical properties and electrical conductivities of CNTs.

The influence of the different proportion contents of CNTs added into epoxy resin on mechanical properties and electrical conductivities of composites is investigated, and strength of material tested under different temperature environments is observed.

Moreover, the creep behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy resin thermosetting composites tested under different temperature and stress is also concerned to be analyzed.

The test results exhibit that mechanical strength and electrical conductivity increase with the increase of CNTs content added into composites. In the influence of temperature effect on specimen, because of different coefficient of expansion among matrix, fiber and CNTs, the overexpansion of matrix caused by high temperature results in crack occurred among matrix. From observation of the fracture surface by SEM, the debonding occurs and longitudinal fibers are pulled out due to poor interfacial combination of fiber and matrix, which also results in entire strength degeneration.

Keywords: Carbon nanotube (CNT) , Scanning electron microscope (SEM) , Creep

INTRODUCTION

Recently, it has been observed that by incorporating nanoparticles or nanotubes into the matrix of fiber reinforced composites[1]. Because of above-mentioned reason, surface modification of CNTs, mechanical strengths[2] and electrical conductivity of thermosetting composites with different proportion content (0.25, 0.5, 0.75 phr) of CNTs, and creep behavior[3] of thermosetting composites tested under different circumstance are considered to be major investigates in this study. The results obtained by testing under different circumstances are adopted to investigate the mechanical strength, electrical conductivity and creep behavior.

EXPERIMENT

Material

MWCNT's employed as a reinforcement in this study are supplied from Desun mammo Co. , /Ltd. (diameter : 30-50 nm, length : 10-200nm, purity : 93%). Hot pressing is adopted for fabricating MWCNT's / epoxy resin prepreg laminate. Epoxy acts as matrix and the pressure at 1000 psi, temperature at 150 °C are requirements for epoxy to shape up. Additionally, modification of CNTs, prepreg material and hot pressing are major requirements for fabricating carbon nanotube / epoxy resin nanocomposites.

Fabrication

First of all, CNTs are dispersed among isopropyl alcohol, then pour surface modification solution, pure water and HCl into the solution of isopropyl alcohol with CNTs, and then stir it for 48 hours at room temperature. After that, place it in heating oven to dry by heat at 100 °C for 24 hours.

After baking, CNTs are dispersed among isopropyl alcohol again, and stir it with Titanium (IV) n-butoxide, (3-aminopropyl) triethoxysilane (APTES) and HCl for 48 hours, and then place it in heating oven to bake again.

All of previous process must be done for modifying CNTs. The mixed solution with great distribution CNTs is poured into liquid impregnation sink first, then the fixed size carbon fiber prepreg is placed into solution. Ultrasonication method is adopted for distributing the mixed solution with CNTs among carbon fiber cloth well.

After completing impregnation, the carbon fiber cloth is placed into heating oven to remove residual solution by baking under the temperature at 50 °C for 6 hours to produce the carbon nanotube / epoxy resin prepreg. After that, the prepregs are piled up into the mold, and hot pressing must be done under pressure at 1000 psi, temperature at 150 °C for 30 min. and then, the prepreg laminates after hot pressing are placed into heating oven again to conduct post hardening for

obtaining great cross linking to proceed to increase the strength of laminates.

Measurement

Tensile strength test, flexural strength test, electrical conductivity test and hygroscopicity test are performed in this study according to the standards of ASTM D3039[4], ASTM D790[5], ASTM D257[6] and ASTM D570-98[7] respectively. Furthermore, the variation of static strength of composites with different CNT content tested under three different temperatures at 25 °C, 85 °C and 175 °C also be investigated. Creep strain tests are carried out and investigated finally.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Static Strength

Fig.1 and fig.2 show the comparison on mechanical strength between unmodified-CNTs/epoxy resin prepreg laminate and modified-CNTs/ epoxy resin prepreg laminate. According to the test results, the mechanical strength of modified-CNTs/epoxy resin prepreg laminate is higher than that of unmodified-CNTs/epoxy resin prepreg laminate.

Fig.3 and fig.4 depict the distribution situation of unmodified CNTs and modified-CNTs among Epoxy resin prepreg laminate observed through SEM. From fig.3, the distribution of CNTs among epoxy resin is poor, and aggregation occurs around local area. Fig.4 shows that the distribution of modified-CNTs among epoxy resin is better and great interface connection between modified-CNTs and epoxy resin without any

aggregation status. Hence, modified-CNTs/epoxy resin prepreg laminate possesses great mechanical strength. According to the mechanical test results, the strength increase with increasing CNTs content. This result indicates that adding content of CNTs plays a crucial role of reinforcement for prepreg laminates.

Fig.5 to fig.6 show the comparison on the different static strengths of modified-CNTs laminates tested under different circumstances.

The decrease ratio of flexure strength of carbon fiber/epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature pretreatment at 85 °C is about 11.5% in comparison with that of CF/epoxy resin laminate tested under room temperature pretreatment. The decrease of strength of CF/epoxy resin prepreg laminate with adding the content of 0.75phr of CNTs tested under the temperature pretreatment at 85 °C is 6.2% in comparison with that tested under room temperature.

The decrease of flexure strength of CF/epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature pretreatment at 175 °C is 15.7% , relative to that tested under room temperature pretreatment. With adding 1 phr of CNTs, the decrease of strength of CF/epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature pretreatment at 175 °C is about 18.1% in comparison with that tested under room temperature pretreatment.

In tensile strength, the decrease of strength of CF/ epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature-moisture pretreatment at 85 °C / 85%RH is around 10.7%, relative to that tested under room temperature. With adding 1phr of modified CNTs, the decrease of strength of CF/ epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature-moisture pretreatment at 85 °C / 85%RH is about 13.6% in comparison with that tested under room temperature pretreatment.

The decrease of tensile strength of CF/epoxy resin tested under the temperature-moisture pretreatment at 175 °C / 85%RH is 16.9%, relative to that tested under room temperature pretreatment . But with adding 1 phr of modified CNTs, the decrease of tensile strength of CF/ epoxy resin laminate tested under the temperature- moisture pretreatment at 175 °C / 85%RH is 17.9% in comparison with that tested under room temperature pretreatment.

The variation of crystalline pattern and cross linking effect caused by temperature variation makes interior structure of material more complicate. Take thermal treatment effect under the temperature at 175 °C for example, the decrease of strength is the most serious.

Under the temperature at 85 °C , the experimental temperature is lower than that of Tg point of material that doesn't lead to a remarkable alteration on cross linking effect of material. When prepreg laminates are tested under the temperature at 175 °C , the lowest mechanical strength occurs due to different coefficient of expansion among matrix, fiber and CNTs. Additionally, the overexpansion of matrix caused by high temperature leads to cracks occurred on matrix. Above-mentioned results also make strength of material lowest.

Under the circumstances at same temperature, the static strength increases with increasing the content of CNTs because the cavities among epoxy resin filled up by CNTs affectively increase Vander Waals' forces, and the functional group bonding created on the surface of modified-CNTs improves the cross linking between CNTs and epoxy resin and improves further on the entire strength of laminate.

Electrical Conductivity

According to the standard of ASTM D257[6], the surface resistivity obtained is shown in fig.7. Because of the great electrical conductivity of CF/epoxy resin laminate with adding CNTs is better than that of CF/epoxy resin laminate. Therefore, the electrical conductivity of CNTs/CF/epoxy resin prepreg laminate increases with increasing CNTs content. Furthermore, the electrical conductivity of CF/epoxy resin laminates with adding modified-CNTs is better than that of CF/epoxy resin laminates with adding unmodified-CNTs. Previous results also infer that the great distribution of modified-CNTs among the matrix do increase entire electrical conductivity of laminate.

Creep Behavior

As shown in fig.8, the creep tests of CF/epoxy resin composite are performed under fixed temperature at 25 °C, and three different stresses. The creep strain of composites increases with increasing stress. Fig.9 shows the creep tests of CF/epoxy resin composite performed under fixed loading of 11.25MPa and three different temperatures (25 °C, 55 °C, 85 °C). The creep strain of composites increases with increasing temperature. Especially, creep behavior occurs notably while specimen is tested under the high temperature at 85 °C. Fig.10 depicts the creep tests of CF/epoxy resin composite performed under fixed loading of 40MPa, fixed temperature at 55 °C and two different relative moistures (60%RH, 90%RH). The creep strain of composites increases with increasing relative moisture.

CONCLUSIONS

1. According to the results of specimens tested under different circumstances, the mechanical strength of modified-CNTs/ epoxy resin prepreg laminate is higher than that of CNTs/ epoxy resin prepreg laminate because the distribution of modified-CNTs among epoxy resin is better and great interface connection between modified-CNTs and epoxy resin without any aggregation status. Hence, modified-CNTs/epoxy resin prepreg laminate possesses great mechanical strength.
2. In the influence on specimen by temperature effect, because of different coefficient of expansion among matrix, fiber and CNTs, the overexpansion of matrix caused by high temperature leads to cracks occurred among matrix.
3. Because of the great electrical conductivity of CNTs, the electrical conductivity of CNTs/CF/epoxy resin laminate is better than that of CF/epoxy resin laminate, and moreover the electrical conductivity of modified-CNTs/CF/epoxy resin laminate is better than that of unmodified-CNTs/CF/epoxy resin laminate. Therefore, the electrical conductivity of CNTs/CF/epoxy resin laminate apparently increases with increasing CNTs content.
4. From the test results of CF/epoxy resin thermosetting laminates tested under the circumstances with different loading, temperature and humidity, loading, temperature and humidity do nonlinearly accelerate the creep behavior.

Fig.1 Tensile strengths of modified CNTs and unmodified CNTs composite

Fig.2 Flexure strengths of modified-CNTs and unmodified-CNTs composite

Fig.3 Dispersion of unmodified-CNTs among the epoxy resin matrix

Fig.4 Dispersion of modified-CNTs among the epoxy resin matrix

Fig.5 Flexure strengths of CNTs/CF/ epoxy resin laminate tested under three different temperature pretreatments

Fig.6 Tensile strengths of CNTs/CF/ epoxy resin laminate tested under three different temperature-moisture pretreatments

Fig.7 Electrical conductivities of modified-CNTs and unmodified-CNTs/CF/epoxy resin laminates

Fig.8 Creep behavior of CF/epoxy resin laminates tested under fixed temperature and three different loadings

Fig.9 Creep behavior of CF/epoxy resin laminates tested under fixed loading and three different temperatures

Fig.10 Creep behavior of CF/epoxy resin laminates tested under fixed temperature, fixed loading and three different relative humidities

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